

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of 3-Furyl and 3-Thienyl-substituted-1,2-benzisoxazoles

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HETEROCYCLIC nuclei play a prominent role in bestowing activity on organic compounds. A survey of the literature revealed that very few benzisoxazoles with heterocycles like furan and thiophene are known¹ because of the difficulty in the synthesis of the starting material. 1,2-Benzisoxazoles exhibit a wide variety of activity like anti-depressant², antibacterial³, tuberculostatic⁴, antifungal⁵ etc. Since an introduction of a heteryl nucleus is likely to modify the activity of benzisoxazoles, a few 3-heteryl-1,2-benzisoxazoles were synthesised.

Various substituted phenols were esterified (I) with 2-furoic and 2-thiophenic acids by the reported procedure⁶. *Ortho*-hydroxy-phenyl-heteryl-ketones (II) were obtained after Fries' migration of these esters. Oximes (III) and *N*-acetates (IV) of the above ketones were prepared⁷ and the corresponding benzisoxazoles (V) were obtained⁸ through *N*-acetates (Scheme 1).

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Experimental

All m.p.s. were taken in an open capillary and are uncorrected. Ir (nujol, ν , cm^{-1}) were recorded on Beckman 120 and 137 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian 100 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ , ppm.

Esterification of phenols with 2-furoic and 2-thiophenic acids was carried out by following the reported procedure⁶.

2-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethyl-phenyl-furyl-ketone: A mixture of heteroyl ester (0.1 mol) and powdered anhydrous AlCl_3 (0.2 mol) was heated in an oil bath at 140-150° for 3-4 h. The complex was decomposed with ice-water containing HCl. The *ortho*-isomer was separated from *para*-isomer by steam distillation and crystallised from ethanol to yield the product (56%), m.p. 114°, ν_{max} 1600 (C=O), 760-720 cm^{-1} (furyl), no hydroxy frequency because of chelation; δ 2.16 (s, 3H, CH_3), 2.18 (s, 3H, CH_3), furyl group protons 6.56 (dd, J 2 Hz, 1H, $\text{ArC}'_4\text{H}$), 7.26 (dd, J 2 Hz, 1H, $\text{ArC}'_5\text{H}$), phenyl group protons, 6.74 (s, 1H, ArC_6H), 7.9 (s, 1H, ArC_6H), 12.5 (s, 1H, OH).

Rest of the ketones were prepared in the similar manner. Physical data of all these compounds are listed in Table 1.

Ortho-hydroxy-phenyl-ketoximes and *ortho*-hydroxy-phenyl-ketoxime-*N*-acetates were prepared by following the reported procedure⁷. Physical data of all these compounds are also listed in Table 1.

3-(2'-Furyl)-5-methyl-1,2-benzisoxazole: Oxime acetate (1 g) and dry pyridine (15 ml) were refluxed for 6 h. Excess of pyridine was then distilled off and the reaction mixture poured on ice-water containing HCl. The product obtained was extracted with ether and washed with dilute aqueous NaOH. Etheral layer was evaporated to get a solid which on crystallisation from ethanol (40%) yielded the product (66%), m.p. 60°; ν_{max} 840 (isoxazole-ring-stretch), 1220 (C-O-N) and 1550 (C=N stretching) and 760-930 cm^{-1} (furyl); δ 2.25 (s, 3H, CH_3), 6.44 (dd, J 2 Hz, 1H, $\text{ArC}'_4\text{H}$), 7.02 (dd, J 2 Hz, 1H, $\text{ArC}'_5\text{H}$), 7.2 (dd, J 2 Hz, 1H, $\text{ArC}'_6\text{H}$) of furyl ring; 7.24 (d, J 2 Hz, ArC_6H), 7.56 (dd, J 2 and 8 Hz, 1H, ArC_6H), 7.6 (d, J 8 Hz, 1H, ArC_7H) of phenyl ring.

All the other cyclised compounds were prepared by following similar procedure and their physical data are listed in Table 2.

Antifungal activity: Fourteen of the compounds (V) listed in Table 2 were tested for antifungal activity by the paper disc method⁹ against *Helminthosporium appaternae*, a wheat pathogen and compound of Sl. no. 14 showed maximum and promising activity (inhibited 57 mm of fungus growth) followed by compounds of Sl. no. 13, 15 and 18. Compounds of Sl. no. 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 19, 20 showed considerable activity, while 6 and 17 were found to be inactive.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS I-IV

Sl. no.	R'	R	Compd. I		Compd. II		Compd. III		Compd. IV	
			M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2'-furyl	H	50 ^a	60	—	60 ^a	134 ^b	50	126 ^b	90
2.	"	2-Cl	65 ^a	90	65 ^b	50	169 ^f	40	102 ^b	70
3.	"	3-OH ₂	43 ^a	70	vis-liq.	35 ^a	126 ^d	25	125 ^d	40
4.	"	4-Cl	87 ^b	90	93 ^b	70 ^a	159 ^d	53	110 ^d	50
5.	"	4-OH ₂	65 ^b	70	73 ^b	65 ^a	120 ^e	80	130 ^b	68
6.	"	2,4-diOl	85 ^a	90	115 ^b	70 ^a	170 ^b	45	134 ^f	50
7.	"	3,4-diCH ₂	58 ^b	77	114 ^b	56 ^a	100 ^d	80	125 ^b	40
8.	"	4-Br	98 ^a	88	90 ^d	70 ^a	160 ^b	65	140 ^b	60
9.	"	2,4-diBr	96 ^a	73	105 ^b	80	170 ^b	40	120 ^b	44
10.	"	2-OH ₂ ,4-Cl	85 ^a	90	140 ^b	60	145 ^b	56	155 ^b	64
11.	"	3-OH ₂ ,4-Cl	69 ^c	92	100 ^b	83	145 ^b	68	124 ^b	97
12.	2'-thienyl	H	59 ^a	50	vis-liq.	30	147 ^b	50	110 ^e	75
13.	"	4-Cl	87 ^b	75	80 ^b	66	125 ^h	58	142 ^b	74
14.	"	4-OH ₂	92 ^c	90	125 ^e	82	119 ^g	66	125 ^e	63
15.	"	3-CH ₂	86 ^a	70	84 ^e	48	160 ^b	50	107 ^e	60
16.	"	3,4-diOH ₂	62 ^a	50	95 ^e	66	117 ^d	50	108 ^b	72
17.	"	2,4-diOl	80 ^a	55	98 ^e	73	169 ^h	63	130 ^b	60
18.	"	2,4-diCH ₂	61 ^a	65	84 ^b	66	146 ^e	60	136 ^b	90
19.	"	2-CH ₂ ,4-Cl	88 ^a	72	56 ^b	66	160 ^d	63	121 ^e	50
20.	"	4-Br	84 ^a	66	58 ^b	66	100 ^e	64	140 ^b	72

Compd. crystallised from : a=Petroleum ether, b=Aq. EtOH, c=MeOH, d=Aq. AcOH, e=Aq. MeOH, f=Benzene, g=Ligroin, h=Toluene + petroleum ether.

*Reported in the literature.

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS V

R' = 2'-furyl (compds. Sl. no. 1-11) ;
2'-thienyl (compds. Sl. no. 12-20)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Activity against <i>H. appatermas</i> Zone of inhibition mm
1.	H	(Thick liquid)	23	—
2.	7-Cl	107 ^a	20	13
3.	6-OH ₂	96 ^a	40	—
4.	5-Cl	104 ^a	29	9
5.	5-OH ₂	60 ^a	66	26
6.	5,7-diOl	150 ^a	29	0
7.	5,6-diCH ₂	115 ^a	32	18
8.	5-Br	117 ^b	24	12
9.	5,7-diBr	149 ^c	11	—
10.	5-Cl, 7-CH ₂	109 ^a	33	11
11.	5-Cl, 6-CH ₂	135 ^a	33	—
12.	H	75 ^a	20	—
13.	5-Cl	104 ^d	25	48
14.	5-OH ₂	50 ^e	20	57
15.	6-OH ₂	—	20	—
16.	5,6-diOH ₂	104 ^f	20	39
17.	5,7-diOl	105 ^a	20	0
18.	5,7-diCH ₂	108 ^a	20	31
19.	5-Cl, 7-CH ₂	100 ^a	45	16
20.	5-Br	89 ^a	15	20

Compds. crystallised from : a=Aq. EtOH, b=MeOH + AcOH, c=EtOH + AcOH, d=MeOH, e=petroleum ether, f=benzene + petroleum ether.

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Synthesis of Possible Antiprotozoal Agents

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BASED on the amebicidal property of emetine several hypothetically modified structural products were synthesised and tested for their antiamebic activity¹⁻⁵. A number of compounds of the types I and II were prepared⁷ and in both these types, the compounds (R=n-hexyl) were appreciably active *in vitro* against *E. histolytica*⁶. A number of